

DIFFERENCES AND SIMILARITIES BETWEEN TWO WORLDWIDE SPOKEN LANGUAGES: CHINESE AND ENGLISH

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Abstract. *This article below concentrates on the differences and similarities between two worldwide spoken languages: Chinese and English, both grammatically and lexically.*

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These days learning a foreign language is the most important aspect of our lives, because if one knows one language he can use this ability to travel and study in another country. In this article, we will see some differences and similarities between Chinese and English, because being aware of them can help one to develop his language fluency. Nowadays, English is the most spoken language in the world, however day by day the number of Chinese learners are also increasing because with Chinese there will be more opportunity to talk with 1. Billion people. Dialects in these two languages differ phonetically, lexically, and grammatically, although the basics of their grammar and vocabulary are the same. Northern Chinese, also known as Mandarin, is the mother tongue of about 70% of Chinese and is the common written language of all Chinese. The English language also has different norms in spelling, vocabulary and grammar depending on the country of the speaker. There are British, American, Canadian, Australian, New Zealand, Irish, Indian and South African English.

Since Chinese modal verbs do not convey such a wide range of meanings, Chinese learners may not use English modal verbs sufficiently. This can lead to the fact that in the course of a conversation, in some cases, the speakers will seem peremptory or rude.

However, there are also many modal verbs in the Chinese language, the only difficulty is that the modal verbs of Chinese are often very similar in meaning to each other and sometimes it is very difficult to distinguish and understand the fine line, shades of meaning. Often, the meaning of a modal verb can change depending on whom the speech is addressed to and with what intonation the statement sounds.

As we can see from these examples, many modal verbs of the Chinese language have very similar meanings and can be understood only in the course of hard practice with exercises and direct communication with native speakers. You should also delve into the culture of China, as it is always inextricably linked with linguistic norms and has a strong influence on them. So, in order to fully understand the meaning of all modal verbs in Chinese, you need to not only learn their original meanings but also learn to capture all the shades and subtleties of the semantic load through reading and talking with the Chinese.

Idioms and short four-character expressions (Chengyu Chinese YDD; pinyin chengyü, literally: "ready expression") are widely used in Chinese to make the language more vivid, lively, and concise. There are not many such short idioms and expressions in English, but there is a fairly rich selection of set expressions, phrasal verbs, and other phraseological units. In English, idioms

can be more specific and direct. In China, the use of four-syllable idioms is mandatory when writing essays, essays, and articles. The more educated a person is, the more idioms he should know, and most importantly, be able to use correctly. Even in the Chinese language proficiency test for foreigners, there is a list of idiomatic expressions that students must master before taking the exam. At the same time, the difference between Chinese idioms and Russian and English ones is that each such expression has a history behind it, a certain legend of origin. There are many idiomatic dictionaries of the Chinese language, where you will find not only the meaning and way of using this or that saying, but also its history, etymology, and analysis by hieroglyphs. The main difference between English and Chinese is the alphabet and tonality.

It is worth noting the main difference between hieroglyphic writing and the alphabet. One hieroglyph carries five hundred times more meaning than one letter since a letter is not a separate semantic unit and a hieroglyph is already a word that includes both phonetic and ideological representations of this word. A letter is just a sign of the alphabet, and only a combination of letters with each other acquires meaning. The hieroglyph is already a complete unit, which has in its composition a phonetic (a way of reading the hieroglyph) and a key (the idea, the meaning of the word).

As in English, Chinese adjectives do not have to match the gender or number of the nouns they modify. In Russian (as in many European languages), if the noun is feminine, the corresponding adjective must also be feminine. Learning any foreign language can be difficult. Some aspects may seem difficult to students, some simple. What is very easy in English can be very difficult to understand when learning Chinese. And vice versa, the rather easy grammar of Chinese can be complicated by the correct use of tones.

Comparative analysis of foreign terms from the field of information technology, mastered by the Chinese language, testifies to the use of existing word-formation methods, primarily semantic borrowing, which makes it possible to construct terms that are phonetically and graphically identical to native Chinese words. As a new phenomenon, the growth in the number of hybrid formations, including abbreviations, should be noted.

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